

Methodology For Improving Geographical Concepts In Primary Education

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Abstract: *In this article, the didactic possibilities of forming geographical concepts in primary education, the further improvement of the content of primary school geography in accordance with the requirements of the times, its central task is the formation of educational activities, the education of schoolchildren in the process of teaching geography in secondary schools. Educational activities, the development and implementation of new pedagogical and information technologies for teaching geography, geographical excursions, further improvement of research technology, specific features of the content of geographical education are discussed.*

Keywords — primary education, geography education, didactic possibilities, natural sciences, geography teaching process, practical methodological problems, teaching forms.

INTRODUCTION.

Improvement of primary education remains an important task in the implementation of the principle of continuity in modern educational conditions. In continuing education, the communication system that ensures the interaction of these main tasks has been striving for the goal of creating a unified education, and finally, today, attention is paid to the fact that teaching and education methods are an important factor in student development [1; p. 14].

In particular, the increasing attractiveness of geographical knowledge as an educational subject in general educational institutions can be realized due to the strengthening of the motivation to study sciences and the formation of the idea that these sciences are a science that studies the world that surrounds us. Knowing and understanding these processes forms the competencies necessary for the future professional activity of a person.

Geographical knowledge creates wide opportunities for students to form a holistic geographical image of the planet, from studying their native land to learning about global laws and processes, getting to the heart of life's problems and finding ways to solve them [2 ;p.78].

A knowledge system is a complex structure consisting of interconnected elements such as concepts, ideas, laws, and facts. These elements are usually manifested in the process of reviewing each topic to ensure that each knowledge system presented in the school curriculum is formed in the minds of students.

Natural sciences are the most important and integral part of human spiritual culture. At the current stage of educational development, the problem of forming general geographical concepts is of particular importance. Modern science is

characterized by its desire to comprehensively and comprehensively cover the studied objects.

"Based on the formation of teaching geography in a modern school, it is necessary to acquire the skills of using statistical data and nomenclature arrays, as well as practical geographical knowledge, in the development of animate and inanimate, i.e., imaginary processes of the world" [3; p. 17].

It is known that in ancient times there was a single science of philosophy, which included the foundations of all natural and social sciences. It can be said that the elements of geographical knowledge are found in almost all ancient nations. Such knowledge was included in the culture of primitive society. Initially, the knowledge mainly related to the geography of the area, and had general information about the surrounding flora, fauna and humanity. At that time, education was mainly carried out in the process of work: adults taught children skills such as gathering medicinal plants, hunting and obtaining building materials.

The main part. Special attention was also paid to conveying folk traditions closely related to environmental protection. In this environment, students observed seasonal changes in the environment, learned to recognize weather signs, and interacted with nature pragmatically, but often with care. He formed teaching methods as people with great life experience and pedagogical skills [4; p. 13].

The need for residential and trade relations with neighbors, wars and other purely vital needs of ancient cultural peoples forced not only to collect geographical knowledge, but also to record it with the help of records. This knowledge mainly belonged to great cultural states such as Ancient Egypt, Phoenicia, India, China and Central Asia.

From the 3rd century BC, that is, during the Hellenistic period, some sciences, first of all, mathematics and medicine, became separate sciences. At the same time, ancient Greek philosophy developed as a natural philosophy, covering not

only philosophical, but also mathematical, natural and social science issues [5; p. 18].

At the end of the 20th century, many countries of the world began to reform the education system, including the improvement of geographical knowledge. The United States was one of the first to understand the need to increase the geographic literacy of the people for the future of their country.

It is known that the low level of geographical education is directly related to the transfer of geography subjects to secondary subjects. Therefore, geography is now included among the five critical subjects in this country. Their in-depth study is recognized as important for the future of the country.

Without a certain level of geographical knowledge, it is impossible to effectively implement ambitious plans for the development of the territory of this great country. Therefore, geography is considered one of the most important school subjects in Brazil.

In some developed countries, people think that the study of geography should now be based on the consideration of the most important geographical problems. In countries that use the French principle of the educational system (France, Ukraine, Latvia, Russia, Poland, etc.), the content of geographical education is mainly developed centrally. In some countries (Austria, Great Britain, etc.) the programs are created directly by the teachers of each school [6; p. 46].

One of the fundamental achievements of modern human consciousness is the emergence and successful development of synergetics as an interdisciplinary direction, understanding the phenomenon of self-organization. Synergetics is already perceived as a warning call to the world community from the surrounding reality.

Synergetics (Greek *synergetikos* - "combined", "coordinated") is a field of scientific research, the purpose of which is "to determine the general (biological, physical, chemical) laws of the formation and stability of ordered temporary and simple structures in complex unbalanced systems in nature."

I. Prigogine was awarded the Nobel Prize for creating the theory of self-organization of matter.

While studying some physical phenomena, the German physicist G. Haken established several new properties of self-organizing systems (hierarchy, energy, exchange of matter and information between hierarchical levels, etc.).

He proposed to call this new scientific direction, that is, the collective effect of many elements, synergetics.

According to E.N. Knyazev and S.P. Kurdyumov, synergetics in pedagogy should be considered in two ways - in the context of the method and within the framework of the educational content. The first aspect is a synergistic approach to education, that is, a method of synergistic organization and management of the education-education process [8; p. 183].

As a result of the emergence of the synergetic doctrine, a post-noclassical view of the world was formed. This is a new

methodological approach to the world. Scientists began to think about society, i.e. people, in a new way.

Ye.O. Kuvandikov summarizes various opinions on the problem of teaching self-organization to the educational system and concludes that it should include the ideas of synergy in the following areas:

"as a method of managing the educational process and a method of knowing and researching the pedagogical process;

designing the content of the subject as educational material necessary for the formation of ideological-methodical and synergistic knowledge and skills;

as a methodical means of implementing the ideas of humanization and integration in the modernization of education;

personal development and cultural values as a pedagogical tool for forming a synergistic way of thinking".

According to its nature, the modern concept of natural sciences incorporates the laws of natural development, genetics, biophysics, geography, and the history of evolutionary development as a complex set of knowledge. This increases their creativity and competence to creative approach to the problem or to strive for their solution [9; p. 18].

The desire to form geographical literacy in elementary school students has a long history in pedagogical education. For example, in the second half of the 18th century, when Kh. Chebotaryev published the textbook "Geographical and Methodical Description of the Russian Empire", general geographical knowledge was given in the 3rd and 4th grades of geography during this period.

At the beginning of the 19th century, geography education was introduced in all educational institutions in European countries and Russia. In particular, the content of G.A. Ponurova's experience of creative activity formed in education was distinguished by I. Ya. Lerner as creative work procedures:

"independent transfer of knowledge and skills in new situations, ability to see problems in familiar situations;

It is explained by the creation of previously known methods of activity as a whole, the creation of a radically new method of solution".

In the research work of A.G. Zakharov, "geographic concept" is defined as follows: "it is a product of consciousness that implies the unity of development of theoretical knowledge, practical knowledge, skills and competencies that lead to a positive change of the person's attitude towards himself and the world around him." [10; p. 29].

Concept is "a generalized form of reflection of the surrounding reality in the human mind. It reveals the essence of the process, the important signs and properties of events and processes, internal communication and relations between them" [11; p. 41].

Thus, the geographical concept is "a generalized form of reality reflection, the content of which is determined by the important features of geographical objects, processes and events, and the relationships between them."

Necessary and sufficient conditions are explained in pedagogical dictionaries as follows:

the existence of necessary conditions for the effective functioning of any system;

adequate conditions are important for the normal functioning of any system.

In the scientific literature, there are different views on defining the concepts of "condition" and "didactic condition", "pedagogical condition". Including:

In the dictionaries, the word "condition" is considered as "a requirement set by one of the parties, an oral or written agreement about something, as well as rules established in any sphere of life and activity.

The place where something was done, the situation in which something happened, the obligatory circumstances that define and condition the existence of something are didactic conditions. Pedagogical condition is a necessary condition that allows to implement, create or contribute to something.

In the encyclopedic dictionary, the concept of "condition" is considered as "a set of factors affecting someone, something, creating an environment in which something happens. The situation describes permanent factors of the social, household and other environment" [15; p. 125].

Researcher A. Bagduyeva states that "pedagogical conditions are the content, forms, methods of the educational process, selected and intended for its application" [13; p. 44].

According to O.Lukhantseva, pedagogical conditions mean a set of specially organized pedagogical conditions that help to increase efficiency, strengthen the effect of the educational process, that is, have a positive effect on its improvement.

I.Aksarina stated that "pedagogical conditions are a set of objective possibilities of content, forms and methods of increasing the efficiency of the educational process and educational spatial environment, which ensure the successful solution of the developed tasks."

Therefore, there may be a case for improving the educational process, which is able to ensure the effective flow of this process to the pedagogical conditions.

In the above-mentioned studies, the concept of "pedagogical condition" is interpreted in different ways and they are explained as follows:

- description of the pedagogical environment;
- factors, ways, directions of the pedagogical process;
- predicted results of the educational process;
- forms, methods and tools.

In particular, the concept as a logical category is distinguished by the content and scope of its two sides, which are interrelated and opposite to each other. According to its content, it is simple and complex, according to its size - individual and general. The elementary school curriculum provides for the formation of individual concepts (Syrdarya, Amidaryo) and general concepts (plants, animals).

"General concepts do not refer to a specific object, event or subject, but serve to describe objects and events called by the same name. Common geographic concepts are also called geographic terms. For example: river, desert, climate, etc.

Specific geographical concepts (like other specific concepts) cannot be conceived in isolation from general concepts." Specific geographical concepts (Amudarya delta, Kyzylkum desert, Ustyurt plateau, etc.) are very close to each other, and also differ from each other in certain aspects. Also, the private geographical imagination reflects an incomplete visual image of existence. Specific concepts, instead of being visual images, reflect the important signs and characteristics of specific subjects or objects. To better understand the difference between imagination and concepts, here is an example:

Desert is a general geographical concept. However, this concept cannot be mastered without imagining the concepts of the desert, the flat surface and the warm climate [18; p. 105].

Natural sciences allow students to form ideas that are the basis for the formation of simple primitive scientific concepts that introduce the laws of the surrounding world, and later become more meaningful in terms of complexity and scope [12; p. 149].

At the end of the 19th century, modern schools were established in our country in order to further develop the nation's development. In modern schools, special attention is paid to the teaching of geography content. O. Mominov divides the textbooks and training manuals published during this period into the following parts: "names.

According to the well-known Methodist scientist N.N. Baransky, "the issue of interrelation between events is the most important issue for the methodology of geography and for the methodology of geography education."

Relationships between geographic objects, events, and processes are key to understanding geography. Geographical cause-and-effect relationships are determined by analyzing the relationships between these elements. Understanding these connections is important in geography education. For example, the formation of the relief, first of all, internal causes: mountain formation, moderate movement of the earth's crust, volcanoes; secondly, external causes are looked at as a consequence of ice cover, marine transgression, i.e. sea encroachment on land, wind and running water.

Yu. V. Mitrofanova states that "the formation of geographical concepts in students based on the individual characteristics of creative activity is a set of skills that allows the development of motivation and reflection".

In her research, N.V. Martilova stated that "on the basis of the study of practical activities in elementary geography education, the formation of creative characteristics of students can be described as a component of the educational content, the process of developing the creative activity of an individual, and the product of creative education. emphasizes" [14; p. 54].

In the research work of I.E. Zhukovskaya, it is mainly "dedicated to the formation of responsible activities of students in the study of urban ecology in the conditions of additional geographical education, in which the experience of creative activity envisages the unity of theoretical knowledge implemented in various types of activities It is described as a unique material and spiritual product that develops a catchy, productive creativity.

V. A. Anuchin's work entitled "Theoretical problems of geography" mainly emphasized that the researches about unity and its role and perspectives in practice are an extremely urgent problem, and in it he advocated the theory of "Uniform Geography". N.N. Baransky and Yu.G. Saushkin gave a wide place to the theoretical issues of economic geography.

By the 21st century, the research works of Uzbek scientists such as I.Q. Nazarov, A.N. Nigmatov, A.S. Soliyev, P.O. Saidov, S.A. Alibekov mainly analyzed some general geographic problems of natural and socio-economic geography, the importance of geographical knowledge in education aimed at clarifying the position.

"Primary school students' geographic competences are expressed by such indicators as being able to understand, master, describe, and guess. Also, the process of developing students' geographical ideas requires active mental activity aimed at long and complex mastery of the cooperative work of the teacher and students.

According to the research of psychologists, the period of 10-11 years of age of children is characterized by the period of transition from primary school age to adolescence. In this period, the period of adaptation is crucial for the child's education or giving up efforts in this direction and self-realization in another way. From the point of view of the development of intelligence, a period of gradual transition from concrete thinking to abstract thinking begins [20; p. 62].

"As a process specially organized by the teacher, carried out in various logical ways, it forms general geographical and individual concepts in students, which requires a targeted approach and tools for solving educational tasks."

The result. From a methodological point of view, there are two main methods of forming geographical knowledge for students:

inductive (from individual to general);

deductive (from general to individual).

Formation of students' geographical imagination is determined by certain conditions:

"regional component capability (that is, the capability to support an inductive path);

deductive style (formation of abstract concepts);

level of formation of educational and cognitive activity methods and intellectual ability;

taking into account the time-consuming nature of the inductive method, it is the duration of training (Table 1.1.1).

Table 1.1.1

T/r	Inductive	Deductive
1.	Monitoring of geographic objects and events	Give the definition of the concept
2.	Distinguishing the signs of the concept by comparing them	Separating and mastering the main signs characteristic of the concept
3.	Generalization	Determine the relevance of the concept
4.	Work on defining the concept	Reinforcement of signs of understanding through exercises
5.	Apply knowledge of the concept in practice	Applying the concept in a new learning situation

It is necessary to follow certain didactic stages for the effective formation of natural and geographical concepts in elementary school students. It is noted that these stages correspond to the characteristics of mental and physiological development of students.

The process of formation of students' geographical concepts has been revealed to a certain extent in the research works of various authors. Including:

H.S. Kostyuk stated that "mastery of concepts in the learning process begins with asking questions and determines the selection of examples necessary for students' cognitive activity, their analysis and subsequent generalization" [17; p. 137].

A necessary condition for successful assimilation of concepts is the presence of students with sufficient emotional experience. In this regard, the use of visualization in mastering concepts is important.

In this case, concepts are the mental representation of certain events and processes in space. Observing processes in nature and society as a geographical fact is very important for students.

It distinguishes two ways of forming concepts:

concrete-practical;

abstract-logical.

In our opinion, the decisive role in the acquisition of concepts belongs to the thinking activity of students controlled by the teacher. "This concept is successfully mastered when students think together with the teacher, compare objects corresponding to a certain concept, distinguish important features, formulate them in the form of opinions, synthesize these opinions, and combine them into a whole".

As an important factor for the successful mastering of concepts by students, systematic organization of educational material, knowledge of its content, scope and connection with other concepts, as well as the optimal ratio of facts and generalizations in it to the abstract and from the abstract to the concrete. Student activity plays an important role when the process of transition and practical application of the concept is formed (Table 1.1.2).

Table 1.1.2

The process of acquiring conceptual knowledge in primary education

<p>Concept</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to know the definition of the concept and apply it in familiar conditions; - to determine the content of the concept, signs, the relationship between the signs, to be able to apply the concept in the performance of educational tasks; - the ability to apply the concept in a new situation.
<p>Cause and effect</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - determining cause and effect with the help of the teacher; - reproducible determination of causality with the help of independent and ready-made plans. - creative application of cause and effect. To be able to use them in new educational tasks.

<p>Skills and competencies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to be able to apply the skill with the help of examples; - application of skills and competencies in reproductive situations; - to be able to apply skills practically in any educational situation.
<p>Ideas of worldview formation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - acquisition of the initial elements of connections between objects and events; - "active thinking, analysis, generalization and systematization" of objects and events; independent generalization of ideas, application of acquired knowledge to the example of new objects and phenomena.

It is worth noting that geography, by its essence, is the change over time of all objects in the nature-society system, the specific features of regional development, and various interconnected national economies. reveals the interconnected aspects of networks [16; p. 358].

In fact, M.M. Shardakov, one of the representatives of the emotional theory of generalization, recommends the formation of educational concepts according to the following stages:

1. Organization of observation of objects or events. The phenomenon is presented to the students with the help of a visual image, new concepts are presented in close connection with the concepts already known to the students. During the entire work process, the attention of elementary school students is focused on general, important signs of the studied topic or events.

2. Enriching observations. For this purpose, observation of various objects and events related to the studied concept is organized. By observing a large number of different new objects and events, students can more easily identify important commonalities, connections and relationships, and secondary individual characteristics.

3. Isolation of important features of the objects and events under study is carried out using the method of abstraction, analysis, synthesis and generalization of individual features of geographical objects and events.

4. Determination. Comparison of geographical objects and phenomena with similar ones in teaching natural sciences of elementary school.

5. Definition of the concept. Once the concept is formed, it is recommended to define it. The definition should include all general and important features of the concepts.

6. Training on practical application of concepts and checking their mastery.

7. Deepening of concepts. In the process of additional education, students become more familiar with the content of concepts and study the relationships between their peers.

According to the author, "at each stage, it is necessary to build a system of explanatory-illustrative, motivational-reproductive, problematic, intra-disciplinary and inter-disciplinary communication, cognitive tasks, use a systematic-structural approach and rationally combine it in educational and research work".

The justification of each stage is to reveal its content, tasks and methods of implementation. At the first stage of this process, students should feel the vital need to learn concepts in order to actively participate in work. As a result of the lack of motivation to the process, one cannot determine the purpose of the activity, and the implementation of motivation is carried out by setting goals.

In the study of basic geographical knowledge, first, under the guidance of the teacher, and then independently, students learn simple cause-and-effect relationships by learning to compare different similar objects, distinguish similarities and differences. they should learn.

"The process of mastering geographical materials, creating wide opportunities for the intellectual, mental and emotional development of the student, puts high demands on the students themselves". Thus, with insufficiently developed cognitive activity, the student cannot fully and correctly perceive and understand the material presented by the teacher.

Debate. A comprehensive approach to learning topics related to geographical objects, phenomena and maps in the content of the "Natural Sciences" textbooks of the primary grade (grades 1-4) ensures the formation of geographical competencies in students [19; p. 41].

A distinctive feature of the "Natural Sciences" program is the continuity and integrity of the formation of the content of the educational course in accordance with the state standard of basic secondary education, the general approaches to education and the main general principles that determine the specific characteristics of the study of natural sciences. education is developed on the basis of the National Curriculum and other normative documents.

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